

2nd TwiNSol-CECs Workshop

Advanced Water Treatments in Emerging Contaminants Mitigation
with Cutting-Edge Technologies

Book of Abstracts

University of Novi Sad
Faculty of Technology Novi Sad
Novi Sad, Serbia

6 - 7 June 2024

2nd TwiNSol-CECs Workshop
*Advanced Water Treatments in Emerging Contaminants
Mitigation with Cutting-Edge Technologies*

Funded by the
European Union

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad,
Novi Sad, Serbia, 6-7 June 2024

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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**Advanced Water Treatments in Emerging Contaminants
Mitigation with Cutting-Edge Technologies**

**University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad (TFNS), Novi Sad, Serbia,
June 6-7, 2024**

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad,
Novi Sad, Serbia, 6-7 June 2024

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Dear colleagues, participants of the 2nd TwiNSol-CECs Workshop,

On behalf of the TwiNSol-CECs team, I am delighted to welcome you all to our 2nd Workshop with title "Advanced Water Treatments in Emerging Contaminants Mitigation with Cutting-Edge Technologies" organized in the frame of TwiNSol-CECs project (GA 101059867). We deeply appreciate your contributions in the form of oral and poster presentations, with the abstracts and full papers compiled in the Book of Abstracts and Proceedings, available on our project website (www.twinsol-cecs.com). We are really proud in securing this project under Horizon Europe patronage and are honored by the opportunities such as this event, enabled through execution of TwiNSol-CECs, to share knowledge and exchange ideas within the environmental research with colleagues from Serbia, Western Balkans, and EU.

This event aims to bring together scientists and experts focused on, but not limited to, the issues on removal of contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) from water by innovative technologies. Since „Cutting-Edge Technologies” in water treatment are part of our focus in TwinSol-CECs project, the 2nd Workshop highlights three key innovative technologies: membrane processes, advanced oxidation, and biosorption. Each of these technologies offers unique and effective approach for removing micropollutants and contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) from water. These innovative technologies, each with its distinct advantages, represent significant advancements in our quest for clean and safe water. By integrating these methods, we can develop more comprehensive and effective strategies for managing water quality and protecting public health.

Beyond these topics, the Workshop also acts as a forum for exchanging research ideas, exploration of complementarities and possibilities for collaboration, contributing to the harmonization of research and innovation efforts crucial for the sustainable transition envisioned by the Horizon Europe and Green Deal calls towards a zero-pollution, toxic-free environment.

The TwiNSol-CECs team wishes you a pleasant stay in Novi Sad and looks forward to engaging discussions on new research ideas and collaborative efforts towards a zero-pollution future,

Prof. Zita Šereš
Chair

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PROGRAM

2nd TwiNSol-CECs Workshop

Advanced Water Treatments in Emerging Contaminants Mitigation with Cutting-Edge Technologies

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Serbia
June 6-7, 2024

Agenda

Thursday – 6 June 2024

Morning session, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Blue Hall
(Chairs: Vanessa J. Pereira and Zita Šereš)

- 9:00 – 10:00 Registration (Entrance Hall of TFNS)
- 10:00 – 10:15 Official opening, Biljana Pajin, Dean of the Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, and Zita Šereš, Chair of the Workshop
- Plenary lectures (30 min per lecture + 5 min for Q&A after each lecture):*
- 10:15 – 10:50 João G. Crespo, Sylwin Pawlowski, Svetlozar Velizarov – **Ion-Exchange Membrane Processes: Perspectives in Water Treatment and Desalination**
- 10:50 – 11:25 Olívia Salomé G. P. Soares – **Catalytic advanced oxidation processes for pollutants degradation**
- 11:25 – 11:55 *Coffee break*
- Invited lectures (15 min per lecture + 5 min for Q&A after each lecture):*
- 11:55 – 12:15 Sanja Panić, Mirjana Petronijević, Igor Antić, Jelena Živančev, Maja Buljovčić, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović – **Heteroatom-doped pyrochar for efficient metal-free catalytic oxidation of contaminants of emerging concern**
- 12:15 – 12:35 Minja M. Bogunović, Ivana I. Ivančev-Tumbas – **Hybrid adsorption/membrane filtration in water treatment for the removal of organic micropollutants**
- 12:35 – 12:55 Nandor Nemestothy, Merve Visnyei, Veronika Kalauz-Simon, Peter Bakonyi – **Gaseous Byproducts in Wastewater Treatment: Challenges and Opportunities with Membrane Technology**
- 13:00 – 14:00 *Lunch*
- 14:00 – 14:30 *Poster session with Coffee*

Afternoon session, Faculty of Technology Blue Hall
 (Chairs: Nandor Nemestothy and Nikola Maravić)

Invited lectures (15 min per lecture + 5 min for Q&A after each lecture):

- 14:30 – 14:50 Snežana Maletić, Jelena Beljin, Irina Jevrosimov, Tamara Apostolović, Srđan Rončević, Marijana Kragulj Isakovski – **The contribution of inoculated biochar to pesticide adsorption and biosorption**
- 14:50 – 15:10 Djurdja V. Kerkez, Milena R. Bečelić-Tomin, Anita S. Leovac Mačerak, Dragana D. Tomašević Pilipović, Dejan Krčmar, Nataša S. Slijepčević, Vesna Z. Pešić – **Sludge application on land: Opportunities and challenge**

Oral presentations (10 min per lecture + 5 min for Q&A after each lecture):

- 15:10 – 15:25 Szabolcs Kertész, Imre Vajk Fazekas, Martin Trancsik, Aws N. Al-Tayawi, József Richárd Lennert, Sándor Beszédes, József Csanádi, Tamás Szabó, Cecilia Hodúr, Gábor Veréb, Zsuzsanna László – **Enhancing the efficiency of low-pressure membrane separations using 3d printed spacers**
- 15:25 – 15:40 Aws N. Al-Tayawi, Hajnalka Csott, Nikolett Sz. Gulyás, József Richárd Lennert, Zsuzsanna Horváth Hovorka, Zsuzsanna László, Cecilia Hodúr, Szabolcs Kertész – **Evaluation of flow dynamics utilizing integrated 3d printed turbulence promoters for mitigation of membrane fouling**
- 15:40 – 15:55 Jelena Molnar Jazić, Tajana Simetić, Marijana Kragulj Isakovski, Aleksandra Tubić, Jasmina Agbaba – **Advanced oxidation processes for natural organic matter and emerging contaminants abatement in water treatment**
- 15:55 – 16:10 Jasmina Nikić, Malcolm A. Watson, Maja Vujić, Jovana Pešić, Jovana Jokić-Govedarica, Srđan Rončević, Jasmina Agbaba – **Addressing arsenic contamination: a polymer-based nanocomposite for water treatment**

Friday – 7 June 2024

Morning session, Faculty of Technology Blue Hall
 (Chairs: João G. Crespo and Szabolcs Kertész)

- 9:00 – 10:00 Registration (Entrance Hall of TFNS)

Plenary lectures (30 min per lecture + 5 min for Q&A after each lecture):

- 10:00 – 10:30 Maria B. Cristóvão, Jorge Bernardo, Andreia Bento-Silva, Maria R. Bronze, João G. Crespo, Vanessa J. Pereira – **Mitigating Anticancer Drug Pollution: Nanofiltration for Control of Emerging Contaminants in Wastewater Effluents**

Invited lectures (15 min per lecture + 5 min for Q&A after each lecture):

- 10:30 – 10:50 Nikola Maravić, Zita Šereš, Jelena Šurlan, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović, Igor Antić, Jelena Živančev, Carla Brazinha, Claudia F. Galinha, João G. Crespo – **Removal of acetaminophen and clarithromycin from water samples using nanofiltration and reverse osmosis**
- 10:50 – 11:10 Vesna M. Vasić, Dragana V. Lukić, Marina B. Šćiban – **Sewage sludge biochar as a sorbent for contaminants of emerging concerns removal from water**
- 11:10 – 11:30 Gábor Veréb, Laura Fekete, Tímea Miklós, Kata Fejes, Renáta Kovács, Ákos F. Fazekas, Erika Nascimben Santos, Szabolcs Kertész, Sándor Beszédes, Cecilia Hodúr, Zoltán Jákói, Gábor Kovács, Zsolt Pap, Tamás Gyulavári, Klára Hernádi, Zsuzsanna László – **TiO₂/CNT-modified pvdf composite membranes for enhanced membrane filtration of oily wastewaters**
- 11:30 – 12:00 *Coffee break*
- 12:00 – 12:20 Dragana, V. Lukić, Vesna, M. Vasić, Marina, B. Šćiban – **Multicomponent adsorption kinetics of micropollutants onto lignocellulosic biosorbents**
- 12:20 – 12:40 Nenad R. Grba – **Nano-geopolymer based remediation techniques for purification of different type of groundwater with high Mn, Fe and other metals/metalloids (As) content**

Oral presentations (10 min per lecture + 5 min for Q&A after each lecture):

- 12:40 – 12:55 Zoltán P. Jákói, Cecilia Hodúr, Sándor Beszédes – **Dielectric monitoring in wastewater-treatment and sludge utilization processes**
- 12:55 – 13:10 Maja Vujić, Vasiljević Sanja, Tajana Simetić, Jelena Molnar Jazić, Marijana Kragulj Isakovski, Jasmina Agbaba, Aleksandra Tubić – **Adsorption kinetitscs of organic pollutants on microplastic fibers in water**
- 13:10 – 14:10 *Lunch with coffee*

Afternoon session, Faculty of Technology Blue Hall
(Chairs: Olívia Salomé G. P. Soares and Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović)

Invited lectures (15 min per lecture + 5 min for Q&A after each lecture):

- 14:10 – 14:30 Ferenc E. Kiss – **Lessons learnt from life cycle assessment of advanced wastewater treatment processes**
- 14:30 – 14:50 Igor Antić, Jelena Živančev, Maja Buljovčić, Dušan Rakić, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović – **Role of a high-resolution mass spectrometry in investigating processes for removal of contaminants of emerging concern from water**

Oral presentations (10 min per lecture + 5 min for Q&A after each lecture):

- 14:50 – 15:05 Marija Šobić, Mirjana Petronijević, Sanja Panić, Igor Antić, Jelena Živančev, Milan Tomić, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović – **Removal of micropollutants from water using hydrochar obtained with process water recirculation**

- 15:05 – 15:20 Arijit Nath, Geremew Geidare Kailo, Abraham Amankwaa, Gabriella Kiskó, András Koris –
Production of Bioactive (Antioxidant and Antibacterial) Peptides from Soybean Milk Proteins by an Enzymatic Membrane Reactor
- 15:20 – 15:40 Concluding remarks

Poster presentations, Central Lobby of TFNS (set-up: June 6, 11:25 – 11:55, dismantling: June 7, 13:10 – 15:40)

- P1** APPLICATION OF PHYSICALLY ACTIVATED BIOCHAR FOR THE REMOVAL OF PHENOL FROM WATER
Aleksandra Adamović, Mirjana Petronijević, Saša Savić, Sanja Panić, Sanja Petrović, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović
- P2** POTENTIAL OF HYDROCHAR AS BIOSORBENT FOR HEAVY METAL IONS REMOVAL FROM WATER
Marco Barbanera, Alessandro Cardarelli, Vesna M. Vasić, Dragana V. Lukić
- P3** INFLUENCE OF SELECTED CARRIER MATERIALS ON NATURAL COAGULANT PRODUCTION YIELD
Sanja Cojbasic, Maja Turk Sekulic, Jelena Prodanovic
- P4** APPLICATION OF LEDs IN UV/CHLORINE AOPs FOR THE TREATMENT OF AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS OF POPs SUCH AS PHARMACEUTICALS
Anett Čović, Luca Farkas, Constance Csaplár, Teodóra Dragić, Tünde Alapi
- P5** PREDICTION THE PHOTOCATALYTIC DEGRADATION RATE OF DICLOFENAC BY ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORKS
S. Roy, L. Das Samanta
- P6** ACTIVATION OF PEROXYMONOSULFATE WITH BIOCHAR - ADSORPTION AND ELIMINATION OF TRIMETHOPRIM ANTIBIOTIC FROM WATERS
Dinesh Chandola, Erik Sinkovics, Zsuzsanna László, Tünde Alapi
- P7** COMBINED ION EXCHANGE AND MICROFILTRATION
Marijana Dragosavac
- P8** LIGNIN DERIVED FROM CYNARA CARDUNCULUS AS AN EFFICIENT BIOSORBENT FOR CHROMIUM(VI) ION REMOVAL FROM WATER
Jorge Gominho, Ana Lourenço, Ricardo A. Costa, Duarte M. Neiva, Vesna M. Vasić, Dragana V. Lukić, Marina B. Šćiban
- P9** JUTE FABRIC WASTE AS A PROMISING ADSORBENT FOR HEAVY METAL IONS AND ORGANIC DYES: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW
Aleksandra M. Ivanovska
- P10** REMOVAL OF PHENOL FROM WATER BY USING FREE AND IMMOBILIZED HORSE RADISH PEROXIDASE CATALYZED PROCESS
Milan P. Nikolić, Slobodanka Stanojević-Nikolić
- P11** PRODUCTION OF ANTIOXIDANT AND ANTIBACTERIAL PEPTIDES FROM SOYBEAN MEAL BY AN ENZYMATICAL MEMBRANE REACTOR
Arijit Nath, Geremew Geidare Kailo, Abraham Amankwaa, Gabriella Kiskó, András Koris

- P12** APPLICATION OF LIGNOCELLULOSIC BIOSORBENT FOR SUGAR JUICE PURIFICATION IN FIXED-BED COLUMN
Lidija E. Perović, Jelena A. Miljanić, Julija Šupljika, Ivan Zdjelarević, Nikola R. Maravić, Zita I. Šereš
- P13** REMOVAL OF CONTAMINANTS OF EMERGING CONCERN FROM WATER USING UV-H₂O₂ ADVANCED OXIDATION PROCESS
Mirjana Petronijević, Sanja Panić, Jelena Živančev, Igor Antić, Dušan Rakić, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović
- P14** Cu²⁺ ADSORPTION FROM AQUEOUS SOLUTION BY WASTE EGGSHELL POWDER
Sanja Petrović, Saša Savić, Mirjana Petronijević, Bratislav Todorović, Staniša Stojiljković
- P15** PHENOL REMOVAL FROM WATER SOLUTION USING PEROXIDASE EXTRACTED FROM POTATO PEEL
Saša Savić, Sanja Petrović, Mirjana Petronijević
- P16** THE MICROPLASTIC IS VISIBLE BY FLUORESCENCE UNDER STEREOMICROSCOPE
Živa Kolenc, Kaja Adamek, Sonja Smole Možina, Anja Klančnik
- P17** THE ADVANTAGE OF LPM LAMPS EMITTING AT 185 NM - A SIMPLE SOLUTION TO ENHANCE THE EFFICIENCY OF PHOTOCHEMICAL WATER POST-TREATMENT PROCESS FOR ELIMINATING NON-BIODEGRADABLE ORGANIC POLLUTANTS
Tünde Alapi, Anett Čović, Luca Farkas, Réka Bíró, Gyöngyi Orosz
- P18** INACTIVE BIOMASS OF THE FUNGUS *Ganoderma applanatum* AND ITS BIOSORPTIVE POTENTIAL FOR REMOVING MALACHITE GREEN FROM WASTEWATER
Natalija Velić, Marija Stjepanović, Jelena Vukoje, Janez Gorenšek, Sandra Budžaki, Marta Ostojčić
- P19** EFFECT OF SODIUM CHLORIDE ON THE REMOVAL OF PHARMACEUTICALLY ACTIVE COMPOUNDS FROM WATER BY A REVERSE OSMOSIS MEMBRANE
Jelena Šurlan, Zita Šereš, Nikola Maravić, Nataša Đurišić Mladenović, Igor Antić, Jelena Živančev, Carla Brazinha, João G. Crespo
- P20** PRELIMINARY PRODUCTION COST ESTIMATION FOR BIOSORBENTS DERIVED FROM PEACH STONES
Danijela Z. Stefanović, Marija R. Miladinović, Biljana S. Đorđević, Milan D. Kostić, Olivera S. Stamenković
- P21** ADSORPTION EFFICIENCIES OF INDIAN NEEM LEAVES FOR REMOVAL OF CONGO-RED DYE FROM AQUEOUS SOLUTION FOR SUSTAINABLE ENVIRONMENT
Radharani Das, Ishita Sinha, Soumyajit Maity, Subhojit Ash
- P22** ADSORPTIVE REMOVAL OF Cr (VI) FROM SYNTHETIC WASTES USING AGRICULTURAL WASTES: A GREEN APPROACH
Radharani Das, G. Roymahapatra, Ishita Sinha, Soumyajit Maity, Subhojit Ash

THE CONTRIBUTION OF INOCULATED BIOCHAR TO PESTICIDE ADSORPTION AND BIOSORPTION

Snežana Maletić*, Jelena Beljin, Irina Jevrosimov, Tamara Apostolović, Srđan Rončević, Marijana Kragulj Isakovski

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Environmental pollution poses significant threats to human health and ecosystems, highlighting the need for effective remediation strategies. Traditional methods of remediation are often costly and time-consuming, driving the search for new, more efficient materials. Carbon-based materials have emerged as promising candidates due to their eco-friendly properties and expanding use in pollution control.

This study investigated sorption experiments in stainless-steel columns (4 cm diameter, 20 cm length) filled with soil amended with biochar pre-inoculated with a biofilm of vegetative cells from *Bacillus megaterium* BD5. To assess the impact of inoculated biochar on pesticide sorption, 0.5% of this adsorbent was added to the total soil mass in the column. Thiourea was used as a tracer at a concentration of around 4 mg/L. Pesticide solutions were then passed through the column, and eluates from the outlet were collected at various intervals and analyzed for pesticide concentrations using GC/MS Agilent 7890 A/5975C.

Analysis involved using a mathematical transport model to solve the advection-dispersion equation (ADE), which provided transport parameters such as retardation (R_d) and biodegradation (λ), as well as breakthrough curves. The retardation coefficient for the compounds investigated ranged from $R_d=40-100$, with Parathion-methyl < Fenthion < Fenitrothion showing an increasing order of retardation. Biodegradation (λ) of the compounds ranged from $\lambda=0.2-3.3$, also increasing in the same order. Interestingly, there was no clear correlation observed between the octanol-water partition coefficient, retardation, and biodegradation, suggesting that hydrophobicity alone did not determine sorption and transport characteristics in these specific conditions. In summary, the introduction of inoculated biochar is likely to enhance the simultaneous adsorption of organic compounds onto the added adsorbents within the porous material and biosorption onto the inoculated biochar. The addition of inoculated carbon-based materials to contaminated sediments demonstrates potential as a remediation technique, effectively inhibiting pollutant leaching to groundwater and facilitating immobilization. This approach holds promise for improving the overall effectiveness of remediation efforts in contaminated environments.

Keywords: Sorption, Remediation, Pesticides, Soil, Groundwater

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